

REQUIREMENTS FOR FUTURE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS TO PLAN THE LESSON PROCESS

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Lesson analysts will fully analyze what kind of tools the teacher has used in the course of the lesson, the effectiveness of this event in strengthening knowledge and the shortcomings in its use, and have a thorough conversation with the teacher.

The methods used by teachers to implement the goal they have set for strengthening the lesson can be approximately:

1. To teach students to be able to repeat exactly the phenomenon, event or definition that they are studying, and in this way to strengthen knowledge.
2. To develop and strengthen the student's ability to give examples from his or her own and others' lives, from the environment, and the ability to think, thereby strengthening knowledge.
3. On the basis of the given knowledge, to solve grammatical exercises, mathematical problems and examples, to achieve the ability to correctly and perfectly solve laboratory work.
4. Cultivating the ability of students to use the facts and concepts obtained from excursions to production in learning subjects.
5. To solve the ideas and opinions of the students on the basis of the learned sources, to develop and strengthen their ability to solve the problem in this way.

These methods used by the teacher in the lesson and their effectiveness are recorded during the analysis. In the process of strengthening knowledge, there are tools that are absolutely necessary to analyze, and they are:

1. Technical means:
 - a) only projection, giving shadows; (epidiascope, filmscope);
 - b) projection, shadow and voice (television, film, etc.);

- c) voice only (radio, tape recorder, etc.);
- g) weapons with permanent instructions (poster, various pictures, table, etc.).
- 2. Weapons with time instruction (marks placed on the student's notebook, various notes shown on the board, etc.).
- 3. Textbook materials (grammar exercises, examples and mathematical problems, laboratory work, etc.).
- 4. Plant-factory developments (herbariums, metal, wooden equipment, etc.).
- 5. Excursion materials (rocks, various plant specimens, leaves, etc.).

Education uses any method or system of methods in the lesson.

It is known that seven different methods are used in Uzbek schools only during the period of teaching literacy.

- 1. Method of adding letters.
- 2. Syllable pronunciation method.
- 3. Whole word method.
- 4. Sound method.
- 5. The synthetic sound method.
- 6. Analytical sound method.
- 7. Analntic-synthetic sound method.

As you know, methods can be public or private. General methods, their analysis and the opinion of the writings about them are interpreted in the general method. These are lectures, explanations, stories and written works, discussions and conversations, independent works based on textbooks and literature recommended for independent reading, laboratory works carried out as experiments, demonstrations and instructions. , consists of exercises, practical training methods and problem-based learning methods.

Professor T. Novatsky divided such methods into simple library and complex methods. It includes simple methods such as lecture, explanation, lecture, interview, written work, discussion, and instructional group methods.

In his opinion, the above methods perform the same task in the lesson. The

method of independent works based on literature does not mean only reading, but also involves making a plan, making a synopsis, performing new tasks born in the process of reading a book, drawing pictures. He puts forward the idea that the general methods of conducting experiments, various exercises and problem-based education can be included in the group of complex methods. I. Makhmutov, it is possible to characterize the methods consisting of a complete system with certain types.

References

1. Dilova N.G. (2021). O‘quvchilarning shaxsiy sifatлари - pedagogik hamkorlikning dastlabki tamoyili. Science and Education. Vol. 2, Issue 10, 558-566 betlar.
2. Расулова З.Д. (2021). Талабаларнинг креативлигини ривожлантиришда масофавий таълимнинг ўрни. Science and Education. Vol. 2, Issue 10, 439-448 бетлар.
3. Dilova N.G. (2021). O‘qituvchi-o‘quvchi hamkorligini vujudga keltirishning pedagogik ahamiyati. Science and Education. Vol. 2, Issue 10, 567-576 betlar.

